

The effects of the disruptive changes due to Covid-19 for Albert Heijn

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ABSTRACT

Covid-19 has severely disrupted the world economy. But whereas offline shopping has taken a heavy hit, online retail has boomed. Especially the grocery retail sector has witnessed dramatic increases in online traffic and demand. The shift in consumer expectations urges grocery retailers to accelerate their digital initiatives. This paper focuses on one digital initiative developed by Albert Heijn, the Albert Heijn Compact app. The development of this app is influenced by and has an impact on, (1) Albert Heijns IT governance structure, (2) the way their business processes are integrated and (3) the cybersecurity risks involved with the implementation of the new app. A new IT Governance structure is proposed, as well as a fitting Business Process Integration solution and risk treatments in order to facilitate the successful implementation of the Compact app.

Keywords

Covid-19, Albert Heijn, IT Governance, Cybersecurity, Compact app, Retail, Business Process Integration.

INTRODUCTION

When the first reports of an unknown virus came in early 2020, no one foresaw the devastating effects it would have on the world. Nine months later, Covid-19 has a strong grip on our lives. Government mandates, lockdowns and travel restrictions have brought economies worldwide to a grinding halt. Millions of workers are being furloughed, there is a strong rise in unemployment and a majority of countries are on the brink of a recession (Jones, Palumbo, & Brown, 2020). Interestingly, the retail sector is less affected by economic downturns, especially the businesses that operate with essential retail items. Grocery and food retailers specifically, saw a 10% increase in sales. But the largest increase came in the form of online shopping. When looking at the Netherlands, supermarkets saw a 32.5% increase in online grocery shopping when looking at pre-and-post

pandemic (Hoeth, Molenaars, & Vervelde, 2020). Research by KPMG (2020) shows that customers view online shopping as a safer alternative compared to regular shopping during the pandemic. Customer safety significantly rose in importance for customers, making it a key influencer. Picnic, already a completely online grocery retailer, responded well to the new reality. Within weeks they moved up the rankings to take the top step in the sector (Nielsen, 2020). This urged offline supermarkets to acknowledge the shift in consumer expectations and to accelerate their digital initiatives.

Especially Albert Heijn, the market leader for grocery shopping in the Netherlands, has already launched multiple initiatives to make their stores more digitally capable in order to provide a better customer experience. But Albert Heijn is not only focussing on the digitalisation of their stores. They are also focussing on their online retail program. One of these initiatives is the Albert Heijn Compact app. The app lets you order groceries which are then delivered for free. This new service affects Albert Heijn in several ways. The scope of this research is, therefore, the impact of the AH Compact app on Albert Heijn its business processes, the changes in governance needed to allow the rapid development and implementation of the app, and the cybersecurity risks involved with the implementation of the new app.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research objective

To investigate how supermarkets can react to disruptive changes, this research conducted a case study on Albert Heijn during the Covid-19 pandemic, and for this purpose, the following research question has been formulated:

“What are the effects of Covid-19 for Albert Heijn regarding their IT governance, business processes, and cybersecurity and risk management, and how should they act accordingly?”

To answer the research question, the following

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sub-questions have been formulated:

1. “What are the pre- and post Covid-19 IT governance aspects for Albert Heijn?”
2. “What are the key processes that have changed as an effect of Covid-19 for Albert Heijn?”
3. “What are the cyber risks as an effect of the change in the key processes in sub-question 2?”

Research approach

IT Governance approach (sub-question 1)

Literature research is used to analyze the most suitable IT governance structure for Albert Heijn. The research is split in pre-Covid-19 and post Covid-19. Literature review on IT governance will be carried out to gain insight into the subject. The focus will be on IT governance in or after disruptive circumstances.

What follows is a conclusion and advice on how IT governance should be structured within Albert Heijn.

Business Process Integration approach (sub-question 2)

By dividing online grocery experience of AH’s customers to pre Covid-19 and post Covid-19 period, and by utilizing BPMN model to visualize which key activities and business processes have been changed, we are going to analyze the impact of Covid-19 on AH’s online grocery service.

Cyber Security and Risk Management approach (sub-question 3)

In order to identify threats for the AH Compact application, Microsoft’s threat modelling methodology (STRIDE) is used. STRIDE is an abbreviation for spoofing, tampering, repudiation, information disclosure, denial of service, and elevation of privilege. These are scenarios that help to identify possible threats. The objective of the STRIDE approach is to get an application to meet the security objectives of an e-commerce system (Affia, 2018). Since the AH Compact application is an e-commerce system, the STRIDE approach is considered suitable for this research and chosen above other threat modelling methodologies.

In order to analyze the threat events and its accompanying security risks, multiple persons participated in the risk analysis to determine the likelihood and impact per security risk as accurately as possible.

SECTOR RESEARCH: RETAIL MARKET

General information retail market

According to Ahold Delhaize’s annual report (2018) retail was and still is a dynamic market, and now, more than ever, consumer demands and emerging technology are driving revolutionary change. Retailers aim to provide greater, more advanced services and goods at tremendous value across platforms. Market demands, too, are increasing. Consumers expect higher quality, more convenience, everything at cheaper rates. In order to give their consumers what they demand and keep ahead of the market, retailers need to be wiser than ever.

The food retail market is developing dramatically and is extremely competitive in the Netherlands. Advancing technology and change in customer preferences are revolutionizing the way Dutch consumers purchase.

Mediabrand Marketing Sciences researched purchasing behaviour of Dutch citizens within the Netherlands. Figure 1 illustrates the outcome of this research and shows the most popular retailers for each branch in the Netherlands.

Figure 1: Waar koopt Nederland?, Mediabrand Marketing Sciences

Focus area: supermarkets (Albert Heijn)

Ahold Delhaize is one of the major grocery retail organizations in the world and a pioneer in supermarkets as well as e-commerce, and a pioneer in sustainable retailing. Each week, Ahold Delhaize serves over 50 million customers. Albert Heijn as a subset of Ahold Delhaize is the Netherlands’ number one food retail company, and the top online retailer.

In the Netherlands, there are five key players on the grocery retail market (Rabobank, 2019). The market share among these five key players is divided as follows:

- Albert Heijn (34,7%);
- Jumbo (19,1%);
- Lidl (10,9%);
- Aldi (6,8%);

- Superunie (29,1%).

In this research, the focus will be solely on the impact of Covid-19 on the digital transformation of Albert Heijn, part of Ahold Delhaize.

Developments in the supermarket industry prior to COVID-19

According to Askew (2019), there are six major trends for the supermarket industry in 2019:

- Tech transforming e-commerce:
 - These technologies include warehouse automation and artificial intelligence (AI).
- Physical stores go digital:
 - Physical stores will offer more digital experiences, for example, mobile applications could help customers to find particular products in the store.
- Personalized experiences:
 - Gathered data of customers will be used (AI and machine learning) to guide people through the shopping experience, this way products and offers can be targeted more effectively.
- The rise of ‘social commerce’:
 - Through social commerce, online shopping could become more social, instantaneous, and convenient.
- Supply chain tech:
 - New possibilities arrive with IoT technologies. For example, live data feeds enable supermarkets to improve their efficiencies of stock deliveries.
- Traceability and data:
 - Via QR codes customers are provided with access to detailed information on the origin of food products.

Also based on an article from McKinsey regarding digital disruption at the grocery stores, five trends are affecting the transformation of the grocery industry. (1) the fight for online shopping customers is on, (2) early movers have the advantage, (3) the scale of the population matters, (4) automation innovation improve economics and (5) the talent gap is a major bottleneck.

Developments in the supermarket industry through COVID-19

As mentioned in section 3.3 there are multiple technical innovations impacting the online and in-store operations of the grocery retailing market. Askew (2019) states that there is a continuation of rapid and radical change in the food and grocery industry, and the pace of change shows no sign of abating in 2019.

According to Park (2020), the Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated change in strategies and technologies used in the food retail sector. In contrast with other business channels, grocery retailers were not dealing with the loss of business amid the pandemic. Grocery retailers had to figure out how to meet a spiking demand across all channels, with online traffic soaring up with 500% for Ahold Delhaize. Furthermore, Park states that customers are becoming more open to digital innovation through online shopping, and the trend toward contactless shopping instore is on the rise.

In conclusion, the digital transformation of the grocery retailing market was already on the rise, but the Covid-19 pandemic accelerated the process significantly.

Digital developments of Albert Heijn

This section provides an overview of the digital developments that took place, processed in a timeline. The timeline is based on information gathered from various sources. The majority of the digital developments are retrieved from the Albert Heijn Erfgoed foundation.

As shown in figure 2 there are two digital developments after the start of Covid-19. Albert Heijn introduced the AH Compact app in order to anticipate the changing customer demands due to the pandemic (Albert Heijn, 2020). Additionally, Albert Heijn accelerated the process of equipping every Albert Heijn store with self scanners, in order to satisfy the strongly growing demand for digital alternatives in shopping (Retailtrends, 2020).

Besides these two digital developments, there are two more significant events after the start of Covid-19 that should be mentioned. Firstly, Albert Heijn (2020) states that the usage of the Appie application increased with 60% over the past year. Secondly, the director of e-commerce from Albert Heijn states that the amount of online ordering increased by 50% over the past year (van Egmond, 2020). In Figure 2, we can see Albert Heijn’s digital transformation journey over the last two decades.

Figure 2: Albert Heijn's Digital Transformation Milestone

ANALYSIS

IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

To answer the first sub-question of this paper, research has been done on IT governance within Albert Heijn. The research is split in pre-Covid-19 and post Covid-19. What follows is a conclusion and advise on how IT governance should be structured within Albert Heijn to remain operational and be able to make swift decisions during and after disruptive changes.

IT governance Albert Heijn pre Covid-19

Ahold Delhaize, the holding company that owns Albert Heijn, publishes an annual report with a specific section on their governance. Ahold Delhaize has set out on a new strategy, called Leading Together. With five growth drivers (omnichannel growth, technology, healthy and sustainable, portfolio and scale efficiencies and best talent), they target to leverage both their scale and local connections. Their strategic statement heavily involves IT. Ahold Delhaize aims to utilize their IT capabilities to grow and to increase business flexibility. Their governance is designed to facilitate strategic and performance goals. Below, a schematic overview of their governance structure can be seen:

Figure 3: Ahold Delhaize's governance structure

The global CIO is part of the executive committee, indicating that their IT investment and prioritization is a strategy call that has been made by the business monarchy, since the CIO of Albert Heijn is not part of this committee, thus ruling out federal intervention.

To further analyze the pre-Covid-19 situation within Albert Heijn, we make use of an interview that was

being held in 2018 with the CIO of Albert Heijn. The interview was held by Hotze Zijlstra. In the interview, Brothers explains: "There was an IT function with a lot of knowledge, commitment and the ability to switch quickly. However, like so many retailers, our company carried the burden of traditional assets. Much of the technology was outdated and there was insufficient investment in the modernization of both applications and infrastructure.

The IT function was not sufficiently connected to the business. The compartmentalization prevented the creation of generic applications for multiple business functions. Centralization was needed in order to create generic applications for multiple business functions. It was up to him to create an IT architecture and infrastructure which would allow the modernization of the technology which would embed the IT function within the business. With a technology roadmap in line with the business strategy, IT and business could jointly determine The IT principles and business applications needed to conform to the global strategy. Using this information, the pre-Covid-19 IT governance structure is the following for Albert Heijn:

Pre Covid 19	IT principles	IT architecture	IT infrastructure	Business application needs	IT investment and prioritization
Business monarchy					
IT monarchy					
Feudal					
Federal					
Duopoly					
Anarchy					

Table 1: Albert Heijn's pre Covid-19 IT governance structure

IT governance Albert Heijn post Covid-19

According to Park (2020), Covid-19 has accelerated change in the strategies and the use of technologies in the food retail sector. But in contrast with other business channels, grocery retailers were not dealing with the loss of business. Instead, it was important to figure out how to meet the spiking demand across all channels, online traffic increased with 500% for Ahold Delhaize.

McKinsey (2020) also reported that in July, the pandemic had already altered the purchasing patterns and behaviours of consumers in the retail sector. These big shifts in spending, purchasing, loyalty, labour costs, footprint and safety might not revert back to the pre-Covid-19 situation.

Before the disruption of Covid-19, there already was a rapid change in customer preferences and competition increase, the Covid-19 disruption has accelerated these developments in an unprecedented

way. In turn, companies in the retail sector had to be agile and adaptive. It is important to note the difference between agile governance and adaptive governance.

Agile governance entails primarily methods and working practices that facilitate quick responses (Beck et al., 2001). On the other hand, “adaptive governance” addresses the ability to deal with complex social problems involving multiple stakeholders, competing interests and confusion about the steps to be taken (Bronen & Chapin, 2013). Adaptivity is essential when facing a major, disruptive change, such as the Covid-19 pandemic (Janssen & van der Voort, 2020).

Thus, we can distinguish two important differences with regard to Albert Heijn’s required IT governance. Before Covid-19, Albert Heijn needed to become more agile as a business. Their IT infrastructure needed to be more connected to the business processes in order to respond more aggressively to changes. However, this had less influence on the adaptability of Albert Heijn, since there was no direct need to quickly respond in order to survive. With the Covid-19 pandemic, their challenge to reduce compartmentalization in order to create generic applications for multiple business functions needs to be accelerated. This requires a shift in the IT Governance structure which leans more towards swift execution.

Using the Governance Design Matrix from Weill (2004), we propose a shift towards arrangement 3, one of the three top-performing patterns Weill has identified. Pattern 3, as shown in table X fits Ahold Delhaize best, since Ahold Delhaize has business leaders who are interested and well-informed about IT issues (see the 2019 annual report). Arrangement 3 is a suitable pattern in times of a crisis when decision rights must be swift, decisive, and tightly held.

Post Covid 19	IT principles	IT architecture	IT infrastructure	Business application needs	IT investment and prioritization
Business monarchy					
IT monarchy					
Feudal					
Federal					
Duopoly					
Anarchy					

Table 2: Albert Heijn’s post Covid-19 IT governance structure

Business Process Integration

In order to be able to answer the second sub-question of research objective, first AH’s growth drivers and digital transformation strategy have been examined. After that for online grocery ordering experience of customers and activities for both pre-Covid-19 and during Covid-19 is shown, and finally how AH has managed to address the challenges regarding responding to the exponential rise of online home delivery.

Business Process Integration of AH pre-Covid 19

In the retail sector, technologies, innovative business models and empowered customers are driving transformation. In reaction to these trends, retailers are transforming. According to the Ahold Delhaize annual report 2019, AH has been continuously searching for effective ways to predict and handle the trend shaping the dynamics of the market and retail sector. AH believes that the trends such as; Technology, Online and Mobile, Convenience, and Operating model of the future are the most important to the retail industry. In alignment with the company’s Leading Together strategy regarding the digital transformation of the organization, AH has intensified its activities in these trends.

By looking at AH’s growth drivers in Figure 3, which are the areas AH has invested in accelerating profitable growth, Technology is one of the 5 pillars of AH’s growth drivers. From both AH’s strategic framework and AH’s growth drivers, we can understand that this organization had special attention toward Technology and digital transformation of its business process.

Figure 4: Growth drivers of Ahold Delhaize

Though growth drivers, especially “Omnichannel growth” & “Technology” AH has accelerated its digital transformation in the food retail industry. Within all stages of the customer journey, via providing an integrated omnichannel service across both offline and online platforms, AH has managed to have the leading customer experience: from preparing to buying. AH has already begun to develop the business model for e-commerce and extend the pick-up and distribution location network.

Constantly striving to develop offline and online channels, and endeavour to deliver inspiring apps, AH has been enabled to offer customers the best mobile experience. In order to help customers to save time, AH delivers more flexible ordering and check-out options.

For online grocery ordering, AH offered two options for customers, either through the Albert.nl or via AH App. Pricing and delivering time for each differs from the other one; as for orders via using the website the minimum order amount is 70 euros, and via using AH App is 50 euros. For delivery fees, customers can select between monthly subscriptions named “Bezorg bundle” for a fixed weekly delivery time window or pay an extra fee depending on their desired delivery time.

According to Figure 4, which depicts activity diagrams for customer’s online grocery ordering experience before Covid-19, we can see that the customer initiated the processes, first by deciding to order via the website or AH App, then either by creating or logging in to an existing account, had a very convenient online shopping experience.

Figure 5: Customer Online Grocery Journey Activity Diagram before Covid-19

Impact of Covid-19

Frans Muller stated that as a result of the Covid-19 outbreak, which has led to an increase in online sales demand, the company accelerated investments in digital and omnichannel capabilities.

Due to the exponential rise in the demand for home delivery, Albert Heijn is facing challenges like small quantity purchases, irregular purchasing patterns and missed delivery windows in the last-mile delivery process. Aforementioned challenges could affect AH’s revenue, therefore for addressing those issues, the company has categorized its last-mile network based on two main factors; “delivery responsiveness” and “product variety”.

For high delivery responsiveness and large product variety, “AH delivery Bundle” and “AH App” were previously offered. But recently, AH has introduced “AH Compact” for lower delivery responsiveness and smaller product variety. For consumers who use the AH Compact app, the required minimum order amount is 35 euros.

Figure 5, depicts the activity diagram for online grocery ordering journey of customers during Covid-19 period. It can be seen that, depending on

consumer needs, AH is trying to offer customer-tailored deals.

Figure 6: Customer Online Grocery Journey Activity Diagram during Covid-19

Conclusion

Albert Heijn created a digital roadmap for business processes, with a focus on creating omnichannel, e-commerce and a better digital experience. Previously they were focused on convenient store checkout options, but Covid-19 triggered an exponential increase in the demand for home delivery. This has not specifically been a focal point for the digital strategy of AH, nevertheless, Albert Heijn managed to introduce a new product to partly solve this problem. This can be seen as the weak link, and according to a report by Capgemini in order to better respond to consumers, Albert Heijn needs to focus more on the Last-Mile delivery challenge.

Cyber Security and Risk Management

The analysis in this section follows the following risk management method steps: define security objectives, analyse the system in context, identify risks, analyze risks, evaluate risks, treat risks, and make recommendations. The analysis will be performed on the recently introduced AH Compact application, and thereby gives an answer to sub-question three.

Security objectives

According to Affia (2018), an e-commerce system consists of three primary (confidentiality, integrity and availability) and three secondary (non-repudiation, authorisation and authentication) security objectives. Since the AH Compact application is an e-commerce system, the mentioned security objectives apply to the AH Compact application as well. The primary security objectives for the AH Compact application are:

- Confidentiality of customer data
- The integrity of product data
- Availability of the AH Compact application

Analysis of the system in context

The system in context is analyzed according to the steps as defined by Refsdal et al. (2015).

The external context of this risk assessment consists of multiple stakeholders. The first stakeholder is KPN, which is the network supplier of the Albert Heijn (van Gaalen, 2019). The second group of stakeholders are the suppliers of Albert Heijn since they are dependent on the purchases made by Albert Heijn. The last group of stakeholders are the customers who buy their groceries at Albert Heijn. Subsequently, Albert Heijn is subject to a number of national laws and regulations regarding its business processes. As part of the identification of the external context, these laws and regulations should be identified and documented. Since Albert Heijn processes a significant amount of sensitive information, ranging from sensitive customer data to sensitive employee data, it is essential to comply with the laws and regulations regarding the GDPR. Failure to comply with these laws and regulations may result in significant financial consequences (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 2019).

The concrete objective of Albert Heijn (2020) is “to be the most popular and healthy company in and for the Netherlands. We make our customers happy. We want to inspire them, surprise them and let them experience our involvement. So that we genuinely matter in all 900 neighbourhoods where our stores are located”. In order to increase their online presence, Albert Heijn is planning to grow significantly in the field of data and digitization. Concretely, this means Albert Heijn has created 150 new jobs in the field of data and digitization, and they already hired fifty data-analysts (Kempe, 2020). Since the introduction of the “Albert Heijn bonuskaart” in 1998, Albert Heijn had to endure several privacy issues regarding the “Albert Heijn bonuskaart”. For example, in 2012, Albert Heijn had to adapt their privacy policy after research conducted by the CBP (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 2012). These privacy concerns in the past are the reason for Albert Heijn for having a strict privacy policy nowadays. In their current privacy policy, Albert Heijn states they believe it is important to ensure that their service provision is transparent, personal and reliable. They claim that they are continuously looking for ways to improve their service in order to align them with the personal wishes and desires of the customer. Furthermore, Albert Heijn handles personal data with care and ensures that all processing of personal data complies with applicable laws and regulations (Albert Heijn, 2020).

The goal of this risk assessment is to identify and reduce the risks of incidents that may happen with the use of the AH Compact application. This is necessary to comply with the earlier mentioned security objectives. The secondary goal is to comply with laws and regulations in relation to privacy and being able to document this in compliance with laws

and regulations.

The target of the risk assessment in this research is the AH Compact application, an e-commerce system by Albert Heijn.

The scope of this risk assessment is limited to risks due to attacks on or via the target of assessment. An action priority matrix for implementing risk treatments lies not within the scope of this risk assessment.

The focus of the risk assessment lies solely on risks associated with the AH Compact application. As mentioned earlier, the AH Compact application was introduced in order to satisfy the changing customer needs due to Covid-19.

In this research, it is assumed that the AH Compact application has identical system features as other e-commerce systems.

This risk assessment will be conducted with respect to Albert Heijn, and more specifically the AH Compact application. The following system assets are identified within the AH Compact application:

- AH Compact login interface
- AH Compact API
- AH Compact server
- AH Compact admin

In order to conduct the risk analysis, this research makes use of a likelihood scale and a consequence scale. The likelihood scale is a 1 to 5 scale, based on a Risk Management Tool constructed by the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (n.d.), and is shown in table 3 in the appendix. The consequence scale is a 1 to 5 custom-designed scale and consists of the following four risk dimensions: reputational, operational, financial and legal/compliance. The reputational, operational and legal/compliance dimensions are based on a Guide to Risk Assessment and Response constructed by the Rochester Institute of Technology (n.d.). The financial dimension is based on the different opinions an auditor can provide to an audit report (NBA, 2016). The consequence scale is shown in table 2 in the appendix.

The risk evaluation is based on the broadly used 5x5 matrix as shown in table 3 in the appendix. For each risk in the risk assessment, the likelihood score will be multiplied by the consequence score. The outcome of the multiplication provides an indication of the risk level, ranging from low (score is one, two or three) till extreme (score is fifteen, sixteen, twenty or twenty-five).

Risk identification and analysis

Affia (2018) conducted research on security risk management of e-commerce systems. The outcomes of this research are applicable in this risk assessment since the AH Compact application is an e-commerce system. Therefore, the identified threat events and security risks in this section are partly based on Affia's research. Following Affia's research, we derive threat events and security risks for the AH Compact application, categorized by threat type according to STRIDE. Subsequently, other risks are identified that do not fit the STRIDE approach, but the risks are significant and should be addressed. A detailed overview of the performed risk analysis is shown in table 4 in the appendix and discussed below.

The first threat type examined is spoofing identity. The identified spoofing identity security risk (SSR1) is that an attacker brute forces access to a valid customer session by comparing valid sessionIDs provided by the AH Compact application. The weak sessionID generated by the AH Compact server is being exploited, which leads to loss of confidentiality of the customer session. The likelihood of this event happening is less than once per year. The risk has a reputational consequence which is that a person would rather not shop at AH anymore (SSR1A). Additionally, the loss of confidentiality of the customer session is a privacy data breach and therefore it can result in significant legal penalties in relation to the GDPR (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 2019) (SSR1B).

The second threat type examined is tampering data. The first identified tampering data risk (TSR1) is that an attacker exploits the insecurely protected AH Compact API and sabotages the product data, which leads to the loss of integrity of product data. The likelihood of this event happening is less than once per year. The risk has a financial consequence because product prices can be adapted. However, the price change is not material and the auditor will give a clean opinion (TSR1A). Subsequently, the risk has a reputational consequence which is that a person would rather not shop at AH anymore (TSR1B).

The third threat type examined is repudiation. The identified repudiation security risk (RSR1) is that an attacker exploits the improper output neutralization to the AH Compact server logs, with means to add entries to the AH Compact server logs to obfuscate prohibited transactions on the AH Compact application. This leads to loss of integrity of the AH Compact process. The likelihood of this event happening less than once per year. When the flow of funds is not transparent, this risk can result in a qualified opinion according to the Dutch GAAP (RSR1A). Additionally, this risk may lead to significant legal penalties if the financial statements are not deposited adequately in compliance with laws

and regulations (RSR1B).

The fourth threat type examined is information disclosure. The first identified information disclosure risk (ISR1) is that an attacker sends SQL injection statements through the AH Compact login interface in order to retrieve sensitive customer data, which leads to loss of confidentiality of customer information. The likelihood of this event happening is less than once per year. The loss of confidential customer information results in damaged customer confidence, where a person no longer shops at AH (ISR1A). Furthermore, this risk can lead to significant legal penalties in relation to the GDPR (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 2019) (ISR1B). The second identified information disclosure risk (ISR2) is that an attacker gains access directory to customer transaction data by querying the AH Compact server for common directory names, which leads to loss of confidentiality of customer transaction information. The likelihood and consequences of this risk are identical to ISR1 and result in ISR2A and ISR2B.

The fifth threat type examined is denial of service. The first identified denial of service risk (DSR1) is that an attacker causes an error state in the AH Compact server, which leads to loss of availability of the AH Compact application service. The likelihood of this event happening is more than twenty times per year. The risk has a reputational consequence which is that a person would rather not shop at AH anymore (DSR1A). Subsequently, the risk has an operational consequence which results in escalating internal and/or external resources that need to be committed to addressing operational challenges (DSR1B). The second identified denial of service risk (DSR2) is that an attacker exhausts the AH Compact checkout service, which leads to loss of availability of the AH Compact checkout service. The likelihood and consequences of this risk are identical to DSR1 and result in DSR2A and DSR2B.

The sixth threat type examined is elevation of privilege (ESR1). The identified elevation of privilege risk is that an attacker gains admin access to the AH Compact application, which leads to loss of confidentiality of AH Compact admin username and password and integrity of AH Compact product data. The likelihood of this event occurring is less than once per year. The risk has a financial consequence because product prices can be adapted. However, the price change is not material and the auditor will give a clean opinion (ESR1A). When product data gets falsified, this risk results in damaged customer confidence, where a person no longer shops at AH (ESR1B). Moreover, this risk can lead to significant legal penalties in relation to the GDPR (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 2019) (ESR1C).

In addition to the identified STRIDE risks,

several other risks worth mentioning are identified. The first identified risk (OSR1) is that an attacker with knowledge of e-commerce develops a fake email identifying as the AH compact application, requesting to pay pending bills (phishing). The AH Compact customer's inability to verify the origin of the email is being exploited, which leads to loss of confidentiality of customer data, and a loss of email integrity. The likelihood of this event happening is almost certain, based on the Albert Heijn 'fake campaign' page (n.d.). The risk has a reputational consequence which is that a person would rather not shop at AH anymore.

The second identified risk (OSR2) is that an employee enters the product price incorrectly, which leads to the loss of integrity of product data. The likelihood of this event happening is estimated at two to five times per year. The risk has a financial consequence, equal to TSR1A, resulting in a clear auditor's opinion (OSR2A). Additionally, the risk also has a reputational consequence which is that a person would rather not shop at AH anymore (OSR2B).

The third identified risk (OSR3) is that the network provider has issues with their network, which leads to loss of availability of the AH Compact application service. The likelihood and consequences of this risk are identical to DSR1 and result in OSR3A and OSR3B.

The fourth risk (OSR4) is that an AH employee works from home in an unsafe environment where he is vulnerable to cyber attacks, which may lead to loss of confidentiality of customer data. The likelihood of this event happening is expected higher as usual due to COVID-19 regulations from the government to work from home. It is likely that this event will happen. The risk has a reputational consequence which is that a person would rather not shop at AH anymore (OSR4A). Additionally, this risk can lead to significant legal penalties in relation to the GDPR (OSR4B).

	Likelihood	Impact	Final score
SSR1A	1	2 (R)	2
SSR1B	1	3 (L)	3
TSR1A	1	1 (F)	1
TSR1B	1	2 (R)	2
RSR1A	1	3 (F)	3
RSR1B	1	3 (L)	3
ISR1A	1	3 (R)	3
ISR1B	1	3 (L)	3

ISR2A	1	3 (R)	3
ISR2B	1	3 (L)	3
DSR1A	5	2 (R)	10
DSR1B	5	3 (O)	15
DSR2A	5	2 (R)	10
DSR2B	5	3 (O)	15
ESR1A	1	1 (F)	1
ESR1B	1	3 (R)	3
ESR1C	1	3 (L)	3
OSR1	5	2 (R)	10
OSR2A	3	1 (F)	3
OSR2B	3	2 (R)	6
OSR3A	5	2 (R)	10
OSR3B	5	3 (O)	15
OSR4A	4	2 (R)	8
OSR4B	4	3 (L)	12

Table 5 - Risk assessment matrix

Risk evaluation

In total, twenty-four risks have been identified. Fourteen of these risks are categorized as low, one as moderate, six as high, and three as extreme. The results of the risk analysis are presented in table 5 'Risk assessment matrix'.

Risk treatment

For each of the identified security risks via the STRIDE approach, the security requirements and its accompanying countermeasure suggestions can be found in Affia's research. Out of these risks, this paper solely discusses the risk treatment of the risks categorized as extreme. The risks categorized as extreme are both a consequence of a denial of service (DSR1 & DSR2). Several security requirements should be put in place to prevent the event from happening, namely, adequate protection tools should be installed in order to monitor the network traffic and set up alerts for disproportionate behaviour. Additionally, a DDoS response plan should be developed.

In this paragraph, the treatment of the other identified risks will be discussed. OSR1 falls in the category of phishing emails, AH has limited influence on customer actions in their personal email. AH should make their customers aware of

phishing emails via their online channels. Via an omnichannel approach, customers can be notified of ongoing campaigns and informed that all other messages are fake. Subsequently, AH should continuously monitor for the activity of phishing emails and take adequate actions. In order to prevent OSR2 from happening, limit- and field checks should be implemented. The third risk can be treated with an appropriate Service Level Agreement with the network provider (KPN). The last risk could be mitigated by providing employees who work from home with a VPN, additionally, employees should get sufficient training in order to create awareness of cyber risks.

Recommendations

We recommend implementing all the suggested risk treatments. However, risk treatments that can be implemented quickly and result in quick wins should be prioritized regardless of the risk score. For risk treatments that require significant resources to implement, appropriate trade-offs should be made between the impact of the risk treatment and the effort.

Cyber resilience refers to the system's ability to recover or regenerate its performance after a cyber-attack produces a degradation to its performance (Linkov & Kott, 2018). According to Brandenburg & Mee (2020), the number of cyberattacks has soared since the Covid-19 outbreak began, as hackers have exploited a greater number of weakly protected back doors into corporate systems as well as the human distraction caused by Covid-19 related events. We, therefore, recommend AH to create company-wide cyber awareness and to become cyber resilient. Accenture (2018) constructed a Cyber Resilience Framework that highlights the critical and continual actions required to achieve Cyber Resilience. The components of the framework consist of the following steps: identity, protect, detect, respond, recover, and anticipate. This framework could be used as a guideline in the process of transforming towards becoming cyber resilient.

DISCUSSION

Prior to Covid-19, Ahold Delhaize had set out a new strategy, called Leading together. This strategic statement heavily involved IT. Ahold Delhaize aimed to utilize their IT capabilities to grow and to increase business flexibility within their retail businesses. In this case, we focus on Albert Heijn.

After Covid-19 struck, it had accelerated change in the strategies and the use of technologies in the retail sector. For Ahold Delhaize, it was important to figure out how to deal with the

enormous demand across all the channels. As stated, online traffic increased by 500%.

The challenge for Ahold Delhaize was to accelerate the transformations which they already wanted to implement prior to the disruptive change of Covid-19. It became important to reduce compartmentalization and increase collaboration between multiple business units. This required a change in their IT governance. We advise Ahold Delhaize to make use of the business monarchy for the key decisions IT principles, IT architecture, IT infrastructure and decisions about investments and prioritization for IT assets. For decisions about Business application needs, we suggest making use of a federal archetype. This shift in IT governance is suitable for operating in uncertain conditions, it enables Ahold Delhaize to take swift and decisive decisions during disruptive circumstances.

Prior to Covid-19 Albert Heijn was able to identify the ongoing trend in online retail business and by formulating a strategic framework and investing in its growth drivers started its journey in the way of digital transformation. More specifically though Omnichannel strategy, it was able to respond to customer needs. By the arrival of Covid-19, demand for home delivery grocery dramatically increased, and AH was facing different types of challenges like small amounts of orders, irregular ordering patterns from customers. For tackling challenges in last-mile delivery processes, AH introduced a new mobile application named as "AH Compact". AH Compact mainly was introduced to respond to the demands of customers with lower amounts of purchases, therefore it has lower product variety and lower delivery responsiveness. Via the use of BPMN approach, changes in processes for online grocery ordering were depicted. We think AH was agile in introducing new service in responding to its customer needs, but it is recommended to invest more in solving its last-mile delivery challenge.

After Covid-19 struck, Albert Heijn implemented the e-commerce application "AH compact". A risk assessment has been conducted on the new e-commerce application to identify risks for Albert Heijn and be able to reduce any incidents that may happen by using the new application.

The AH Compact application was introduced in order to satisfy the changing customer needs due to Covid-19. These changing needs are also mentioned in the IT governance research. In total, twenty-four risks were identified in the risk assessment. Six of these were identified as high and three as extreme risks. Our recommendation is to implement all the risk treatments that are mentioned, also the treatments elaborated by Affia (2018). It is important for Albert Heijn to utilize the knowledge gained by this research. By implementing the

proposed IT governance structure, Albert Heijn will be able to respond swiftly and quickly on possible risks and incidents that might occur.

CONCLUSION

The objective of this research was to investigate how supermarkets can react to disruptive changes, the unit of analysis was Albert Heijn during and after the Covid-19 pandemic. A newly IT governance structure is proposed where a business monarchy is leading as an archetype for most of the key IT decisions. Also, a risk assessment is conducted for the newly introduced e-commerce application "AH compact". Several risks are identified in the risk assessment. Subsequently, possible measures to mitigate these risks are proposed.

This research has multiple constraints which can be related to Covid-19. Due to constraints that Covid-19 has caused interviews could not be held to gather insight knowledge from professionals, for example in the field of cybersecurity.

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APPENDIX

Figure 2: Albert Heijn's Digital Transformation Milestone

Figure 3: Ahold Delhaize's governance

Figure 4: Customer Online Grocery Journey Activity Diagram before Covid-19

Figure 5: Customer Online Grocery Journey Activity Diagram during Covid-19

Table 1: pre Covid-19 IT governance

Table 2: post Covid-19 IT governance

Table 3: 5 x 5 matrix (likelihood * consequence)

		Consequence				
		Negligible 1	Minor 2	Moderate 3	Major 4	Catastrophic 5
Likelihood	5 Almost certain	Moderate 5	High 10	Extreme 15	Extreme 20	Extreme 25
	4 Likely	Moderate 4	High 8	High 12	Extreme 16	Extreme 20
	3 Possible	Low 3	Moderate 6	High 9	High 12	Extreme 15
	2 Unlikely	Low 2	Moderate 4	Moderate 6	High 8	High 10
	1 Rare	Low 1	Low 2	Low 3	Moderate 4	Moderate 5

Table 4: likelihood scale

Likelihood value:	Description:	Multiplier:
Rare (0 - 10%)	Less than once per year	1
Unlikely (10 - 35%)	Once per year	2
Possible (35 - 60%)	Two to five times per year	3
Likely (60 - 90%)	Six to twenty times per year	4
Almost certain (90 - 100%)	More than twenty times per year	5

Table 5: consequence scale

Consequence:		Impact to:			
Rating	Multiplier	Reputational (customer confidence) (R)	Operational (availability AH Compact application) (O)	Financial (F)	Legal/Compliance (L)
Negligible	1	No damage (a person still shops at AH)	Modest resources need to be committed to internal operational issue	Clean opinion according to the Dutch GAAP	No regulatory or legal action
Minor	2	Potential damage (a person rather not shops at AH)	Escalation of resources that need to be committed to address operational issue	Clean opinion according to the Dutch GAAP	Minor legal penalties
Moderate	3	Damaged (a person no longer shops at AH)	Escalating internal and/or external resources need to be committed to address operational challenges	Qualified opinion according to the Dutch GAAP	Significant legal penalties; operations under surveillance internally
Major	4	Significantly damaged (a large group of persons rather not shops at AH)	Significant internal and/or external resources need to be	Disclaimer of opinion according to the Dutch GAAP	Operations under surveillance by external regulatory

			committed to address operational issues		body
Catastrophic	5	Loss of confidence (a large group of persons no longer shops at AH)	Widespread or long-term shut down of operations.	Adverse opinion according to the Dutch GAAP	Cessation of programs/operations by regulatory body

Table 4: Risk assessment matrix

Threat type:	Threat event:	Security risk:	Likelihood:	Impact:	Final score:
Spoofing Identity (S)	An attacker brute forces access to a valid customer session by comparing valid sessionIDs provided by the AH Compact application.	SSR 1: An attacker brute forces access to a valid customer session by comparing valid sessionIDs provided by the AH Compact application. The weak sessionID generated by the AH Compact server is being exploited, which leads to loss of confidentiality of customer session.	1	2 (R) 3 (L)	SSR1A: 2 SSR1B: 3
Tampering Data (T)	An attacker exploits the insecurely protected AH Compact API and sabotages the product data.	TSR 1: An attacker exploits the insecurely protected AH Compact API and sabotages the product price, which leads to the loss of integrity of product data.	1	1 (F) 2 (R)	TSR1A: 1 TSR1B: 2
Repudiation (R)	An attacker exploits the improper output neutralization to the AH Compact server logs, with means to add entries to the AH Compact server logs to obfuscate prohibited transactions on the AH Compact application.	RSR 1: An attacker exploits the improper output neutralization to the AH Compact server logs, with means to add entries to the AH Compact server logs to obfuscate prohibited transactions on the AH Compact application. This leads to loss of integrity of the AH Compact process.	1	3 (F) 3 (L)	RSR1A: 3 RSR1B: 3
Information Disclosure (I)	An attacker sends SQL injection statements through the AH Compact login interface in order to retrieve sensitive customer data.	ISR 1: An attacker sends SQL injection statements through the AH Compact login interface in order to retrieve sensitive customer data, which leads to loss of confidentiality of customer information.	1	3 (R) 3 (L)	ISR1A: 3 ISR1B: 3
	An attacker gains access directory to customer transaction data by querying the AH Compact server for common directory names.	ISR 2: An attacker gains access directory to customer transaction data by querying the AH Compact server for common directory names, which leads to loss of confidentiality of customer transaction information.	1	3 (R) 3 (L)	ISR2A: 3 ISR2B: 3
Denial of Service (D)	An attacker with the intention to cause an error state in the AH Compact server.	DSR 1: An attacker causes an error state in the AH Compact server, which leads to loss of availability of the AH Compact application service.	5	2 (R) 3 (O)	DSR1A: 10 DSR1B: 15
	An attacker with the intention to exhaust the AH Compact checkout service.	DSR 2: An attacker exhausts the AH Compact checkout service, which leads to loss of availability of the AH Compact checkout service.	5	2 (R) 3 (O)	DSR2A: 10 DSR2B: 15

Elevation of Privilege (E)	An attacker gains admin access to the AH Compact application. and integrity of AH Compact product data	ESR 1: An attacker gains admin access to the AH Compact application, which leads to loss of confidentiality of AH Compact admin username and password and integrity of AH Compact product data, since the attacker can modify the data.	1	1 (F) 3 (R) 3 (L)	ESR1A: 1 ESR1B: 3 ESR1C: 3
Other (O)	An attacker with knowledge of e-commerce develops a fake email identifying as the AH Compact application, requesting to login and pay pending bills (phishing).	OSR 1: An attacker with knowledge of e-commerce develops a fake email identifying as the AH Compact application, requesting to pay pending bills. The AH Compact customer's inability to verify the origin of the email is being exploited, which leads to loss of confidentiality of customer data, and a loss of email integrity.	5	2 (R)	OSR1: 10
	An employee enters the product price incorrectly.	OSR 2: An employee enters the product price incorrectly, which leads to the loss of integrity of product data.	3	1 (F) 2 (R)	OSR2A: 3 OSR2B: 6
	The network provider has issues with their network.	OSR 3: The network provider has issues with their network, which leads to loss of availability of the AH Compact application service.	5	2 (R) 3 (O)	OSR3A: 10 OSR3B: 15
	An employee works from home in an unsafe environment where he is vulnerable for cyber attacks.	OSR 4: An employee works from home in an unsafe environment, where he is vulnerable for cyber attacks, which may lead to loss of confidentiality of customer data.	4	2 (R) 3 (L)	OSR4A: 8 OSR4B: 12